

THE STRUCTURAL COMPUTATION OF SARS-COV- 2 : A LIMITATION

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ABSTRACT :

In this paper we will try to compute a most important bio-physical property of Covid19 as an analogy of other biopolymers (1,2) like proteins – viruses . Since Covid19 is also considered as one of the most fatal viral biopolymer under this pandemic phase an attempt has been made through statistical computation of best fit regression.(3) An input -output data modelling of bi-variant study of Molecular Weight (M) – Radius of Gyration (Rg)(4) with standard coding (5) will be referred . Finally a **limitation** of statistical computation is discussed with reproducibility (6) of SARS – COV-2 mutants.

Keywords : SARS-COV-2 , , Biopolymers , MMF Regression , Hydrodynamic Properties , Reproducibility .

INTRODUCTION :

Covid19 a m-RNA virus having a outer sphere of capsule consists of spike protein (SP) nucleocapsid as well as non-protein (NP) (7)part responsible for viral pathogenic attack . The Molecular Weights of the recombinant proteins was already determined by elution chromatography (SDS – PAGE) are determined as 180 kDa, 110 kDa and 35 kDa for the corresponding subunits by **Tingting Li et al (7)**. Main **objective** of this study is to correlate the hydrodynamic properties like radius of gyration (Rg) - molecular weight (M) of Covid19 with other biopolymers through MMF-regression statistics (8) followed by a standard coding (JSON)(5) with the **limitations** (6)of computations with reference to infection fatality (8)

METHODS :

1. Software used – Curve Finder 1.4 .

2. Data Input (4) – A [2x2]square matrix of M (KDa) – Rg (nm) in the following set of standard data-set **Figure –I (4)**of different biopolymers from proteins – viruses ranging as bellow :

M (KDa) Rg (nm)

10	1.5
20	2
50	2.5
100	3.5
200	4.5
500	6
1000	8.5
0	0

Figure – I

Figure – II (Scattered data - plot of input data set Rg- M)

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION :

The **output data modelling** of MMF-Regression (9) are referred as Figure –III & Figure – IV .

The above set of [2x2] data -matrix is executed by Curve Finder 1.4 through MMF regression fit with Chi-Sq variation , Cov -Matrix [4x 4] (10), Pearson (r) coefficient , Standard error (s) to represent best fit regression as following results .

Figure – III (Standard Curve)

Figure –IV (Correlation data)

Where variables (y) and (x) are Radius of Gyration (Rg) and Molecular weight (M) and a,b,c,d are coefficients of regression respectively .

Figure (III) is represents a standard curve of different globular proteins – viruses and **Figure (IV)** relevant with a Pearson – correlation (r) coefficient = 0.9978 , standard error (s) = 0.2342 (**p-value < 0.0001 @ 0.01 interval**).also represents standard calibration curve (**Figure – III**) for variation of Rg vs Molecular weight of biopolymers of proteins and virus molecule .

Computation of Radius of Gyration (Rg) of a specific value of Molecular Weight of (M) of Covid19

For SARS-COV-2 molecular weights of the subunits (7) -180KDa ,110KDa ,35 KDa the value of Rg as computed from **Figure –III** are **3.9 nm ,2.95 ,and 0.7 nm** respectively . A **JSON-coding (5)** may be considered as final computation of data modelling.

CONCLUSION :

The main **limitation (6)** of this computation is the bio-physical property (11) under consideration ie Rg value(2) can't be correlated with fatal nature of nucleocapsid protein of the subunits. The Rg data of any biopolymers generally represents the random nature of the same correlating biological properties .But theoretical computation (12) of Rg value **3.9+ _2.95 +_0.7 nm under the study** can't be directly correlated to the fatality of infection or community spreading due to lack of reproducibility(6) of the SARS-COV-2 mutants .

CONFLICT OF INTEREST : I shall declare that I have no conflict of interest / competing interest .

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